

Supporting Information for

Flexible, Print-in-Place 1D-2D Thin-Film Transistors Using Aerosol Jet Printing

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Figure S1. Schematic diagram illustrating the working mechanism of an ultrasonic atomizer and aerosol jet printer nozzle. In the ultrasonic atomizer (left), ink is aerosolized *via* ultrasonication and the ink vial is pressurized by an inert carrier gas flow (in this work N_2), which forces the combined aerosolized ink and inert gas flow towards the deposition head. In the deposition head (right), the aerosolized ink flow is focused by an annular inert gas sheath flow (in this work N_2) and directed towards the substrate. The line printed on the substrate usually has a width between 50 and 100 μm for the inks and nozzle diameters used in this work. Apart from focusing, the sheath flow also avoids the direct contact between the aerosol stream and the inner wall of the nozzle, which reduces the risk of nozzle clogging.

Figure S2. Optical images illustrating the device structure after each step in the process flow including a) printing the CNT channel, b) rinsing the channel with toluene, c) printing the S/D electrodes, d) printing the gate dielectric and e) printing the gate electrode.

Figure S3. The impact of ink additives. a) Photo of 2 μL h-BN ink droplets with different compositions. Optical images of 2 μL h-BN-water dispersion droplets b) without any additives, c) with 0.11mg/mL HPMC and 5.7% v/v propylene glycol (PG), d) with HPMC only, and e) with PG only. The droplets are dried on a Kapton substrate at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, and it is shown that PG suppresses the coffee-ring effect while HPMC enhances substrate adhesion.

Figure S4. Cross-sectional SEM images of the AgNW/h-BN/AgNW stack a) with and b)-c) without HPMC as an additive for both AgNW and h-BN ink. Heterostructures printed in the absence of HPMC exhibits worse interfacial properties.

Figure S5. a) Schematic diagram illustrating the fabrication process of a h-BN capacitor including I) masking the Kapton substrate with another piece of Kapton, II) evaporating Au/Cr as the bottom electrode, III) printing the h-BN dielectric layer and IV) printing the AgNW top electrode. b) Optical image of a h-BN capacitor on 127 μm Kapton substrate.

Figure S6. Dependence between the thickness of the aerosol jet printed h-BN films and the number of printing passes. a) Photograph of printed h-BN films with different numbers of printing passes on SiO_2/Si substrate, for each number of printing passes, 3 squares of h-BN films are printed. b) Thickness of the printed h-BN squares acquired *via* profilometry measurement. c) Linear fitting between the number of printing passes and the corresponding film thickness. Each data point is the average from three printed films with error bars denoting the quadratic means of roughness (standard deviation of each measurement).

Figure S7. a) Impedance spectroscopy result of printed h-BN capacitors indicating an ideal capacitor behavior over the frequency range of the measurements. Inset is a circuit diagram

illustrating the model of ‘leaky capacitor with equivalent series resistance’.¹ The linear feature indicates an ideal capacitor behavior over the frequency range between 1000 Hz to 10⁶ Hz, with negligible effective series resistance and leakage. b) Parallel resistance extracted using the parallel R-C model and plotted as a function of frequency. The reduction in R_p at higher frequencies is attributed to the effective charging and discharging of the capacitors.¹

Note S1. A more rigorous estimation on gate capacitance and channel mobility.

To get a more rigorous estimation on the CNT network mobility, we re-modeled the gate capacitance using the equation $C_{ox} = (C_{\infty}^{-1} + C_Q^{-1})^{-1}$. C_Q is the quantum capacitance, and $C_{\infty}^{-1} = \frac{1}{2\pi\epsilon} \ln((\Lambda_0/R) * \sinh(\pi * 2d/\Lambda_0)/\pi)$, where d and $\epsilon = \epsilon_0 * \epsilon_r$ are the thickness and the dielectric constant of the gate dielectric layer respectively, R represents the radii of CNTs and Λ_0^{-1} is given by the linear density of CNT network. $\Lambda_0^{-1} \approx 4 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ is extracted from Fig. 1d, $\epsilon_r \approx 3.01$ and $d = 2.54 \mu\text{m}$ are extracted from Fig. 3c and Fig. S4c respectively. Assuming $R = 0.65 \text{ nm}$ (given by NanoIntegris) and neglecting the quantum capacitance contribution, yields a gate capacitance $C_{ox} = 0.99 \text{ nF/cm}^2$, which is slightly lower than the measured results from Au/h-BN/AgNW capacitors. Therefore, the mobility extracted using the equation $\mu = (L_{CH}g_m * C_{ox}) / (W_{CH} * V_{DS})$ is slightly higher than what is extracted from the parallel-plate model.

Figure S8. Subthreshold characteristics of a printed CNT-TFT with both drain and gate current plotted. The gate current is on the same order of magnitude as the OFF-state current and the noise level of the probe station, indicating minimal gate leakage.

Figure S9. Electrical performance of an in-place rinsed 1D-2D TFT including a) subthreshold, b) transfer and c) output characteristics

Figure S10. Hysteresis characteristics of printed TFTs. a) Subthreshold characteristics of a printed 1D-2D TFT showing forward and backward sweeps with negligible hysteresis. The scan rate was 4.0 V/s. b) Distribution of hysteresis among 11 1D-2D TFTs under the same scan rate. c) Hysteresis of a printed 1D-2D TFT plotted as a function of scan rate. The voltage difference between the linear-fitted forward and backward sweep when the current is half of I_{on} is taken as the hysteresis. Most of the printed TFTs have a hysteresis lower than 1V, and the highest hysteresis is less than 5V from a gate sweep of 80 V. There is no significant difference between the hysteresis of in-place rinsed devices and externally rinsed devices.

Figure S11. Effect of annealing on a printed 1D-2D TFT. a) Subthreshold and b) transfer characteristics were measured before, right after, one day after, and 3 days after annealing. Right after 150°C annealing for an hour, the printed 1D-2D TFT experiences a moderate negative shift in threshold voltage and reduction in transconductance. However, the effect is not lasting as the transfer characteristics recover and stabilize after a single day in ambient condition.

Figure S12. 1D-2D TFTs printed on paper. a) Photograph of 1D-2D TFTs printed on paper using a maximum process temperature of 80°C . b) Subthreshold characteristics of a printed 1D-2D TFT on paper with both drain and gate current plotted.

Table S1. Comparison between the maximum process temperature and mechanical flexibility achieved in this work and that of previously reported printed flexible CNT-TFTs. Note that strain is usually not given directly by the references, the equation $\epsilon \approx t / 2r$ is used to estimate the strain.

Reference	Printing method	Dielectric material	Electrode material	Maximum process temperature °C	r mm	t μm	$\epsilon \approx t / 2r$ %
This work	Aerosol jet printing	h-BN	Silver nanowires	80	2	127	3.2
2	Inverse gravure printing	BaTiO ₃ (BTO)*	Silver Nanoparticles (AgNP)	150	1	~100	~5
3	Aerosol jet printing	PVP/pMSSQ	AgNP	150	1	25	2
4	Screen printing	BTO*	Silver ink	125	5	-	-
5	ink-jet-like	BTO / PMMA	Silver nanoparticles	180	1 / folding	10	0.5 / -
6	Screen printing	BTO*	Silver ink	140	3	-	-
7	Aerosol jet printing	Ion gel	PEDOT:PSS, Evaporated Au	105	-	-	-
8	Microplotter	BTO / PDMS	Unsorted CNT	150	Stretchable	500	60

* Although only BTO is mentioned as the material for gate dielectric, it is possible that a polymer phase is included as in reference 5.

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